

Supplementary Information

Engineering the Cellular Microenvironment: Integrating 3D nontopographical and 2D biochemical cues for precise control of cellular behavior

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Supplementary Figures:

Figure S1. Illustration of cell growing on different substrates. A) schematic representation of cells interfering with flat surface (left) and a nanopillar structure (right). This figure highlights the different proteins involved in the focal adhesion and curved adhesion on nanopillars. B) Immunofluorescent images showing the cellular response to the flat and nanopillar substrates. Vinculin highlights focal adhesions, where the merged images illustrate the spatial relationship between the nucleus, focal adhesions, and cytoskeleton. This demonstrates a higher presence on the flat surface and reduced presence in the nanopillars. Blue: nucleus, Green: Vinculin, Red: Actin, (Scale bar=20 μm)

Figure S2. Dose optimization for the light induced protein patterning. Average fluorescent intensity of FITC-gelatin micropatterns as a function of the UV exposure dose.

A)

B)

Figure S3. Nanopillar micropatterning with different shapes. A) FITC-gelatin protein patterned absorbed on the patterned area with various shapes on nanopillars. B) Profile of protein intensity across a line on image 1D.

Micro-contact Printing

Light Induced Protein Patterning

Figure S4. Comparing micropatterning on nanopillars with different methods. Confocal microscopy reconstructed images of patterned FITC-gelatin on micropillars with micro-contact printing (top) and light induced protein patterning (bottom). Light induced protein patterning demonstrates the effectiveness of micropatterning with PRIMO system that can deposit protein not only on the sides of pillars, but also on the surrounding of pillars. Scale bar 5 μm .

Figure S5. Immunofluorescent imaging of cells on different substrates. A) Cells grown on a flat surface, B) Cells cultured on a nanopillar substrate, displaying different morphological changes with cells stained with phalloidin (red) and DAPI (blue) to highlight nuclei.

Figure S6: NSI to CSI ratios on micropatterned nanopillar substrates. The plot illustrates NSI to CSI ratios for cells on various shaped micropatterned nanopillars compared to non-patterned nanopillar controls. Notably, the highest NSI to CSI ratio is seen with rectangle 10, indicating a comparatively more cellular deformation than nuclear deformation.